

1 **Title:** Microbial richness and composition independently drive soil multifunctionality

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3 **Running title:** Microbial drivers of soil multifunctionality.

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32 **Abstract**

- 33 1. Soil microbes provide multiple ecosystem functions such as nutrient cycling, decomposition and
34 climate regulation. However, we lack a quantitative understanding of the relative importance of
35 microbial richness and composition in controlling multifunctionality. This knowledge gap limits
36 our capacity to understand the influence of biotic attributes in the provision of services and
37 functions on which humans depend.
- 38 2. We used two independent approaches (i.e. experimental and observational), and applied
39 statistical modeling to identify the role and relative importance of bacterial richness and
40 composition in driving multifunctionality (here defined as seven measures of respiration and
41 enzyme activities). In the observational study we measured soil microbial communities and
42 functions in both tree- and bare soil-dominated microsites at 22 locations across a 1200 km
43 transect in southeastern Australia. In the experimental study we used soils from two of those
44 locations and developed gradients of bacterial diversity and composition through inoculation of
45 sterilized soils.
- 46 3. Microbial richness and the relative abundance of γ -Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria and
47 Bacteroidetes were positively related to multifunctionality in both the observational and
48 experimental approaches; however, only Bacteroidetes was consistently selected as a key
49 predictor of multifunctionality across all experimental approaches and statistical models used
50 here. Moreover, our results, from two different approaches, provide evidence that microbial
51 richness and composition are both important, yet independent, drivers of multiple ecosystem
52 functions.
- 53 4. Overall, our findings advance our understanding of the mechanisms underpinning relationships
54 between microbial diversity and ecosystem functionality in terrestrial ecosystems, and further
55 suggest that information on microbial richness and composition needs to be considered when
56 formulating sustainable management and conservation policies, and when predicting the effects
57 of global change on ecosystem functions.

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59 **Key words:** Bacteria, Enzyme activities, BEF relationship, Nutrient cycling, Terrestrial ecosystems

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63 **Introduction**

64 The status of Earth's biodiversity is in decline (Dirzo *et al.* 2014). The loss of species has global
65 consequences because biodiversity promotes ecosystem functions and services that are essential for
66 human well-being (Hooper *et al.* 2005; Cardinale *et al.* 2012). These services include food production,
67 nutrient cycling and climate regulation; and have been valued at trillions of U.S. dollars per year
68 (Costanza *et al.* 1997). The importance of biodiversity for ecosystem functions and services has been
69 shown (Cardinale *et al.* 2011; Tilman *et al.* 2014), however, biodiversity is extremely complex, and
70 involves different components including, but not limited to, species richness (number of taxa) and
71 composition (i.e. identity of the different organisms comprising a community expressed in terms of
72 their relative abundance; Díaz *et al.* 2001). Both taxa richness and composition have been reported to
73 influence one or several ecosystem functions (Díaz *et al.* 2001; Hooper *et al.* 2005; Flynn *et al.* 2011;
74 Isbell *et al.* 2011; Allan *et al.* 2013; Dooley *et al.* 2015; Lefcheck & Duffy 2015). Variation in
75 composition can act in synergy or opposition to effects of richness in natural (rather than randomly
76 assembled experiments) systems, and thus, the role of different aspects of diversity (composition,
77 richness, identity) remains unclear (Wardle *et al.* 1999; Leps *et al.* 2001; 2004). Moreover, the relative
78 importance of these two biodiversity metrics for increasing the provision of several ecosystem
79 processes simultaneously (multifunctionality) remains largely unexplored (Isbell *et al.* 2011; Byrnes *et al.*
80 *et al.* 2014a,b; Dooley *et al.* 2015). Both species richness and composition are likely to change markedly
81 under future climatic scenarios or more intense land uses (Díaz *et al.* 2001; Hooper *et al.* 2005).
82 Therefore, it is critical that we quantify the relative importance of these biodiversity components for
83 multifunctionality so that we can formulate appropriate management and conservation policies and
84 predict the likely changes in ecosystem functioning under changing environments.

85 Unlike plants or animals (Hooper *et al.* 2005; Lefcheck *et al.* 2015), we have only a limited
86 understanding of the relationships between microbial diversity and composition, and ecosystem
87 functioning, particularly in terrestrial environments (Bardgett & van der Putten 2014). Microbes are
88 considered by far the most abundant and diverse life forms on Earth (Singh *et al.* 2009), and play
89 essential roles in maintaining multiple ecosystem functions including litter decomposition, primary
90 production, soil fertility and gaseous emissions (He *et al.* 2009; Peter *et al.* 2011; Jing *et al.* 2015;
91 Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* 2016). Global environmental drivers such as land use change, nitrogen
92 enrichment and climate change are impacting upon both soil microbial diversity and composition (Wall
93 *et al.* 2010; Gans *et al.* 2005; Maestre *et al.* 2015). In order to evaluate the global consequences of

94 shifting microbial diversity on multifunctionality, it is critical that we account for the independent
95 effects of species richness and composition on multiple ecosystems functions (Downing & Leibold
96 2002; Hooper *et al.* 2005).

97 A growing body of experimental and observational studies suggests that microbial diversity
98 promotes ecosystem multifunctionality in terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (He *et al.* 2009; Peter *et al.*
99 2011; Jing *et al.* 2015; Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* 2016). For example, Peter *et al.* (2011) provided
100 experimental evidence for a link between microbial richness and ecosystem multifunctionality in
101 bacterial aquatic biofilms. Moreover, using field surveys, He *et al.* (2009), Jing *et al.* (2015) and
102 Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* (2016) found strong positive relationships between microbial alpha diversity
103 and multifunctionality from local to global scales. Much less is known, however, of the role of
104 microbial composition in driving multifunctionality. Recently, whole genome sequencing (Trivedi *et al.*
105 2013) has provided evidence that dominant bacterial groups such as Actinobacteria phyla and
106 Proteobacteria classes (e.g. γ -Proteobacteria) can potentially play different roles in supporting critical
107 ecosystem processes such as decomposition and nutrient cycling. However, despite these findings, we
108 still lack empirical evidence from either observational or manipulative studies of the roles of these
109 microbial taxa in supporting multifunctionality in terrestrial ecosystems. Only recently, studies based
110 on plant communities have started explicitly considering the simultaneous effects of both plant
111 composition and diversity in driving multifunctionality (Isbell *et al.* 2011; Dooley *et al.* 2015; Lefcheck
112 & Duffy 2015) Conversely, to the best of our knowledge, no study has statistically evaluated the
113 relative importance of soil microbial richness and composition (i.e. relative abundance of main phyla
114 and classes) in controlling multifunctionality. Assessing the relative importance of microbial diversity
115 and composition in driving multifunctionality is critical to include microbial communities and
116 processes in ecosystem and earth system simulation models, and to consider their status when making
117 policy or management decisions.

118 Herein, we combined a regional field survey and a microcosm experiment manipulating the
119 diversity of bacteria in two soils to identify the role and relative importance of microbial richness and
120 composition in predicting multifunctionality. We hypothesized that microbial richness and composition
121 are both important, but operate independently, as drivers of terrestrial multifunctionality. Our rationale
122 is that microbial richness and composition represent two different mechanisms controlling
123 multifunctionality. First, for microbial interaction (complementarity effects; Loreau & Hector 2001):
124 theoretical frameworks (Schimel *et al.* 2005) predict that complex processes such as chitin degradation

125 (Beier & Bertilsson 2013), require a large and diverse group of microbes. Second, regarding microbial
126 identity: whole genome sequencing information indicates that different microbial groups can potentially
127 play idiosyncratic roles in ecosystem processes such as organic matter decomposition and nutrient
128 cycling, which may potentially affect the rates in which these processes are being produced (Floudas *et*
129 *al.* 2012; Trivedi *et al.* 2013).

130

131 **Material and Methods**

132 Study sites and soil sampling.

133 We used two independent but complementary approaches to evaluate the role and relative importance
134 of microbial richness and composition in supporting multifunctionality: an observational study that
135 utilized a broad regional soil survey (Field survey), and an experimental microcosm approach
136 (Microcosm study). Note it is not our intention to directly compare results between experimental
137 approaches. Rather, our goal is to address our research question by using two very different, but
138 complementary, approaches (experimental and observational studies) and thus provide further rigorous
139 scientific support to our findings. We define microbial richness as the number of taxa (microbial
140 phyla/classes) and microbial composition as the identity of the different microbial taxa comprising the
141 soil community (in an environmental soil sample or microcosm), expressed in terms of relative
142 abundance.

143 Rationale of the use of observational and experimental approaches to identify the role of microbial 144 richness and composition in controlling multifunctionality.

145 Observational data (e.g. changes along a broad environmental gradient) provide useful information on
146 how bacterial diversity and composition relate to multifunctionality under “real world” scenarios.
147 However, because of the observational nature of this approach, results are correlative and potentially
148 non-causative. Conversely, using an experimental, laboratory-based microcosm with cultures provides a
149 unique opportunity to manipulate both bacterial richness and composition, generating multiple
150 combinations of these two biotic features. The use of cultures alone, however, is usually considered
151 unrealistic because the majority of bacterial taxa are unculturable and there are difficulties in
152 assembling bacterial communities *de novo* (Hooper *et al.* 2005; Bell *et al.* 2005). Culturing is useful
153 however for comparing the results with other ecological studies (Loreau & Hector 2001; Hooper *et al.*
154 2005). Using both observational and microcosm experimental studies gives us a unique opportunity to
155 separate the differential effects of taxa richness and composition on multiple ecosystem functions.

156 *Field survey (observational approach).*

157 Our observational study was carried out in 22 sites from eastern Australia across a gradient of about
158 1200 km (Fig. S1; Table S1). Locations were intentionally chosen to represent a wide range of climatic
159 and soil property conditions. Mean annual precipitation ranged from 280 mm to 1167 mm and
160 temperature from 12.8° C to 17.5°C. Soil organic carbon (soil carbon) and pH ranged from 0.8 to 12.3%
161 and from 4.8 to 9.0, respectively (Table S1). Soil sampling was carried out in March 2014. At each site,
162 three soil cores (0-5 cm depth) were collected from two microsites: under trees (*Eucalyptus* spp.) and in
163 open (bare soil) -dominated sites. Soil cores were then mixed to obtain a composite sample for each
164 microsite at each site. A total of 44 soil samples (22 sites x 2 microsites) were analysed in this study.
165 Following field sampling, the soil was sieved (<2 mm mesh). A portion of the soil was immediately
166 frozen at -20°C for characterizing bacterial abundance, composition and diversity. The other fraction
167 was air-dried and stored before functional analyses. This storage approach is well established and
168 commonly used when analyzing soil variables such as those evaluated here in large-scale surveys
169 (Maestre *et al.* 2012; Tedersoo *et al.* 2014).

170 Soil DNA was extracted from 0.25 g of defrosted soil samples using the Powersoil® DNA
171 Isolation Kit (Mo Bio Laboratories, Carlsbad, CA, USA). We quantified the abundance of total bacteria
172 in all soil samples (Field and Microcosm studies) using 96-well plates on a CFX96 Touch™ Real-Time
173 PCR Detection System (Foster city, California, USA). Bacterial 16S rRNA gene was amplified with the
174 Eub 338-Eub 518 (Lane 1991) primer set as described in Maestre *et al.* (2015). We characterized
175 bacterial diversity and composition in the soil surface (top 5 cm) along our observational gradient by
176 using the Illumina Miseq profiling of ribosomal genes (Illumina Inc.) and the 341F/805R (Herlemann
177 *et al.* 2011) primer set (see details in Appendix S1).

178 *Microcosm study (Experimental approach).*

179 In parallel with the sampling protocol described above, we collected a greater mass of soil (~5kg) from
180 two sites of contrasting aridity and total soil carbon (Soils A and B; Fig. S1; JM072-TREE and Site 1-
181 TREE in Table S1). Soil A had a lower soil carbon than Soil B (3.03% vs. 8.45%). In addition, Soil A
182 had a higher pH than Soil B (6.36 vs. 5.63; Table S1). In both cases, soil samples were collected from
183 under tree canopies. Following field sampling, the soil was sieved (<2 mm mesh), one part stored
184 immediately at 4°C (non-sterile soil used for the microbial inoculums), and the other sterilized using
185 gamma radiation (50kGy; Appendix S1).

186 The richness treatment consisted of one, two, four and six bacterial taxa per microcosm. For
187 each of these richness levels, we prepared all the possible equally distributed taxa combinations. A total
188 of 37 (6+15+15+1 combinations corresponding to richness levels one, two, four and six) treatments
189 were prepared per soil. We duplicated the level “six” of diversity to improve the balance of this
190 treatment and to ensure the success of this important level of diversity (6+15+15+2). In addition, and to
191 reduce the correlation between diversity and composition in our experiment, we also prepared
192 additional microcosms with diversity ‘two’ but with 75/25% and 25/75% of bacterial composition to
193 reduce correlation between taxa richness and composition. This is a critical point, as most previous
194 biodiversity research has not adequately separated composition effects from richness effects due to
195 experimental design constraints (Huston, 1997; Allison, 1999; Hooper *et al.* 2005). This provided 30
196 new treatments per soil (Table S2). A total of 67+1 combinations were used in this study (a complete
197 list of combinations is shown in Table S2). To ensure the success of our inocula, we established three
198 microcosms for each combination (68 x 3), resulting in a total of 204 microcosms per soil (Soils A and
199 B).

200 Bacterial strains from six terrestrial dominant phylogenetic taxa belonged to phylum
201 Actinobacteria, Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes, and Proteobacteria classes α -Proteobacteria, β -
202 Proteobacteria, and γ -Proteobacteria (Fig. S2), were isolated across both Soils A and B (Appendix S1
203 for isolation details and rationale of the selection of these phyla/classes).

204 Sterile soil samples (10 g) were placed in hermetic containers. Soil samples were inoculated to
205 achieve a total amount of 10^8 cells per microcosm. Thus, the final cell densities in all microcosms were
206 the same, that is, the six-taxa assemblage had the same number of cells (1/6 of each strain) as those in
207 the single taxon assemblage. These microcosms were positioned in a laminar flow cabinet to avoid
208 contamination. Microcosms were incubated in the darkness at 50% soil water content (SWC) and 25°C
209 for 8 weeks under sterile conditions. Soils were opened to the air every 5 days in a laminar flow cabinet
210 to prevent the samples becoming anaerobic. After incubation, a portion of the soil was immediately
211 frozen at -20 °C, and the abundance of different bacterial taxa determined using quantitative PCR
212 (qPCR). This step is critical as it provided us with information on the degree to which the original
213 microbial combinations were maintained in our microcosms. The other fraction was used to assess
214 multiple ecosystems functions as described below. Soil DNA extraction and bacterial 16S rRNA gene
215 quantification were done as explained above (i.e., Field survey).

216 To check whether the original composition assigned to the different microcosms was maintained
217 by the end of the experiment and take into account changes in bacterial abundance in our microcosms,
218 we quantified the abundance of each of Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes and α -, β - and γ -Proteobacteria
219 and Firmicutes using qPCR (Appendix S1). Both original assigned (when microcosms were constructed)
220 and corrected (after qPCR analyses) relative abundances of bacteria were highly related (Spearman ρ
221 >0.935 ; $P < 0.001$ in all cases) so we used the corrected values in further analyses.

222 Rationale for the selection of high bacterial taxonomic ranks: phyla/classes.

223 Our decision to use high bacterial taxonomic ranks to explore the role of microbial richness and
224 composition in controlling multifunctionality (i.e. Microcosm study) is based on three main reasons: (1)
225 the main phyla/classes are globally distributed and common across samples (e.g. Ramirez *et al.* 2012);
226 (2) The use of high bacterial taxonomic ranks (phyla and classes) has been highly recommended to
227 predict patterns in ecosystem functioning (Philippot *et al.* 2010; Trivedi *et al.* 2013); (3) functional
228 information has become increasingly available at this taxonomic level (Fierer *et al.* 2007; Bastian *et al.*
229 2009; Trivedi *et al.* 2013). This is critical, as understanding how changes in taxa richness and
230 composition influence ecosystem functions requires an understanding of the functional characteristics
231 of the taxa involved (Hooper *et al.* 2005).

232 Rationale for the selected phyla/classes.

233 We selected *Actinobacteria*, *Bacteroidetes*, *Firmicutes* and α -, β - and γ -*Proteobacteria* for three main
234 reasons: (1) All of these bacterial taxa are globally distributed and dominant in many terrestrial
235 ecosystems worldwide (Fierer *et al.* 2009; Maestre *et al.* 2005); 2) the selected taxa are all easy to
236 culture under laboratory conditions (see *Microbial isolation* below); and 3) quantitative PCR (qPCR)
237 specific primer sets are available for all these bacterial taxa (i.e. see Microcosm study below).

238 Measurement of individual ecosystem functions.

239 In all soil samples, we measured seven variables (hereafter functions): activity of β -glucosidase (starch
240 degradation), cellobiosidase (cellulose degradation), N-Acetylglucosaminidase (chitin degradation),
241 phosphatase (phosphorus mineralization), basal respiration and glucose and lignin induced respiration.
242 Extracellular soil enzyme activities: β -glucosidase, cellobiosidase, N-Acetylglucosaminidase and
243 phosphatase were measured from 1g of soil by fluorometry as described in Bell *et al.* (2013). In
244 addition, we used the MicroResp® approach from Campbell *et al.* (2003) to measure basal respiration
245 and glucose and lignin-induced respiration. For the Field study, soil samples were pre-incubated at 50%
246 SWC and 20°C during five days prior to MicroResp® analyses (Garcia-Palacios *et al.* 2011). Samples

247 with (glucose and lignin) and without (basal respiration) substrates were incubated for 6 h and read at
248 570 nm. Substrate induced respiration of glucose and lignin are calculated as respiration in glucose or
249 lignin less the basal respiration. Altogether, the selected soil variables (hereafter functions) constitute a
250 good proxy of nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, biological productivity, and buildup of
251 nutrient pools (Campbell *et al.* 2003; Schade & Hobbie 2005; Perroni-Ventura *et al.* 2009; Jax 2010;
252 Maestre *et al.* 2012; Bell *et al.* 2013; Bradford *et al.* 2014; Jing *et al.* 2015). Extracellular enzymes such
253 as β -glucosidase, cellobiosidase, N-Acetylglucosaminidase and phosphatase are produced by soil
254 microbes, and are involved in the processing, stabilization, and destabilization of soil organic matter
255 and nutrient cycling in terrestrial ecosystems (Bell *et al.* 2013). They are also considered a good
256 indicator of nutrient demand by soil microorganisms (Bell *et al.* 2013). In addition, basal respiration
257 and glucose induced respiration have been used as a proxy of microbial activity in soil, while lignin
258 degradation provides a metric of the capacity of a particular microbial community to degrade
259 recalcitrant carbon (Campbell *et al.* 2003).

260 Assessing multifunctionality.

261 We used three complementary approaches to evaluate the role of microbial diversity and composition in
262 driving multifunctionality: averaging multifunctionality, multiple-threshold method of Byrnes *et al.*
263 (2014a) and multiple single functions. These multifunctionality indexes were independently obtained
264 for the soils in Field and Microcosm studies and also for the Soils A and B in the Microcosm study. It is
265 important to clarify that our intention is not to merge these two soils included in the Microcosm study,
266 but to ensure that our hypotheses are valid after using different experimental approaches and two soils
267 with different soil properties. To obtain an averaging multifunctionality index for each sample, we first
268 normalized (log-transformed when needed) and standardized each of our seven ecosystem functions
269 using the Z-score transformation as described in Maestre *et al.* (2012). Following this, the standardized
270 ecosystem functions were averaged to obtain a multifunctionality index (Maestre *et al.* 2012).
271 Averaging multifunctionality is widely used in the multifunctionality literature and provides a
272 straightforward and easy-to-interpret measure of the ability of different communities to sustain multiple
273 functions simultaneously (Maestre *et al.* 2012; Wagg *et al.* 2014; Bradford *et al.* 2014; Jing *et al.* 2015).
274 However, we stress that the averaging multifunctionality approach explained above also has some
275 limitations. For example, the averaging approach cannot distinguish between (1) two functions having
276 similar values and (2) one function having high values compensating for a second function with low
277 values (Byrnes *et al.* 2014a). To overcome these limitations, we also estimated multifunctionality using

278 the multiple-threshold method of Byrnes *et al.* (2014a), which evaluates the number of functions that
279 simultaneously exceeds multiple critical thresholds. In brief, this approach calculates the maximum
280 value of each measured function and counts the number of functions that exceed a pre-established
281 threshold. For our analyses, we used predetermined thresholds (Byrnes *et al.* 2014a; Bradford *et al.*
282 2014). Here, we selected three thresholds (25, 50 and 75%) that cover the whole spectrum. This method
283 provides information about the threshold in which our variable maximizes the effect on the number of
284 functions beyond that threshold. In our case, these thresholds inform about the functional level in which
285 more functions are maximized with richness increments and shifts in composition. Our averaging
286 multifunctionality index was highly related to the number of functions at or above 25, 50 and 75%
287 thresholds of the maximum observed function, supporting the appropriateness of our approach
288 ($P < 0.001$; Table S4). Thus, for simplicity, we conducted the main analyses in this study using the
289 multifunctionality averaging approach.

290 Statistical analyses.

291 *Exploring the relationship between bacterial diversity/composition and multifunctionality.*

292 For the Field survey (non-replicated approach), we first explored the relationship between bacterial
293 richness and composition (α -, β - and γ -Proteobacteria, Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes and Actinobacteria)
294 with multifunctionality and each single function by fitting linear multiple regressions. In addition, we
295 conducted partial correlations between bacterial richness and composition with multifunctionality
296 accounting for latitude/longitude and total bacterial abundance (qPCR) to take into account any bias
297 derived from these important factors. Bacterial diversity was x^2 -transformed to improve normality
298 before these analyses.

299 For the Microcosm study (replicated approach), we examined the effects of diversity on
300 multifunctionality by conducting a nested ANOVA, with diversity as a fixed factor and bacterial
301 combination (Table S1) as a random factor nested within diversity (Quinn & Keough 2002). We
302 repeated these analyses using bacterial abundance as a covariate (ANCOVA) to account for any bias
303 derived from a potential shift of bacterial yield in our microcosms. We then used Spearman's
304 correlations to explore the relationship between the relative abundance of the main bacterial
305 phyla/classes with single functions, averaging multifunctionality and with the number of functions at or
306 above 25, 50 and 75% thresholds of the maximum observed function. Finally, we evaluated the effects
307 of each bacterial phyla/classes identity in supporting multifunctionality in both mono- and mixed

308 cultures (i.e. presence or absence of each taxon across all microcosms) by conducting ANOVA
309 analyses.

310

311 *Distance-based multimodel inference*

312 To identify the relative importance of richness and composition of bacteria (α -, β -, γ -Proteobacteria,
313 Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes and Firmicutes) as drivers of multifunctionality, we used a multi-model
314 inference approach based on information theory and non-parametric distance-based linear regressions
315 (DISTLM; McArdle and Anderson 2001). We did these analyses using the PERMANOVA+ for
316 PRIMER statistical package (PRIMER-E Ltd., Plymouth Marine Laboratory, UK). The Euclidean
317 distance was used as the measure of multifunctionality dissimilarity between pairs of samples. Bacterial
318 richness represents the number of inoculated phylotypes in the case of our Microcosm study, and the
319 number of OTUs (species) of all bacteria in the case of our Field survey. In the Microcosm study, the
320 composition of bacteria represents the relative abundance of the six inoculated taxa. In the case of the
321 Field survey we used two approaches to represent the composition of bacteria including: (1) relative
322 abundance of the six selected taxa (those in our experimental approach) accounting for 28-74%
323 (average 53%) of the relative abundance of all bacteria. Thus our aim was to directly compare results
324 from our field and experimental approaches; and (2) a representation of the composition of the entire
325 community of bacteria (100% of species) (using the axes from a NMDS). To obtain a metric of
326 community composition at the lowest taxonomic rank, we used a non-metric multidimensional
327 ordination (NMDS) on the matrix of bacterial composition at the OTU level (i.e. species level). Given a
328 low stress in these analyses (0.05), the axes of a NMDS are considered a good representation of the
329 variation in the composition of entire bacterial communities across samples. We kept the three-
330 dimensional NMDS solution for further analyses. We conducted NMDS ordinations with the package
331 Vegan from R (Oksanen *et al.* 2015) using the Bray-Curtis distance. Including a representation of the
332 entire community composition of bacteria in our models is needed to clarify the relative importance of
333 bacterial composition and diversity in driving multifunctionality in the Field survey (i.e., real world)
334 where multiple bacterial species co-exist together.

335 In addition to these analyses, for the Field survey we repeated our model including richness and
336 composition of bacteria, spatial variables (latitude and longitude) and soil properties (soil carbon and
337 pH). Finally, for the Field survey, we also repeated our analyses including spatial influence, soil
338 properties, bacterial richness, and composition at the OTU level (using the axes from a NMDS) instead

339 of only including selected microbial taxa in this study (α -, β -, γ -Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria,
340 Bacteroidetes and Firmicutes).

341 We ranked all the models that could be generated with our independent variables according to
342 the second-order Akaike information criterion (AICc). Here, we consider a $\Delta\text{AICc} > 2$ threshold to
343 differentiate between two substantially different models and then select the best of those models
344 (Burnham and Anderson 2002; Burnham *et al.* 2011). Then, we compared the AICc of the best model
345 including both taxa richness and composition to that of the corresponding model with only composition
346 or richness. Differences < 2 in AICc between alternative models indicate that they are approximately
347 equivalent in explanatory power (Burnham and Anderson 2002). Finally, we calculated the relative
348 importance of bacterial richness and composition (relative abundance of six selected taxa) as predictors
349 of multifunctionality as the sum of the Akaike weights of all models that included the predictor of
350 interest, taking into account the number of models in which each predictor appears (Burnham and
351 Anderson, 2002; Maestre *et al.* 2012). It is important to note that, in general, our analyses were not
352 influenced by high collinearity between richness and composition, as only weak relationships were
353 found between bacterial richness and composition for both Field and Microcosm studies (Table S3).

354 *Partial correlation*

355 We conducted partial correlation analyses to thoroughly check whether the relationship between
356 bacterial richness or composition was still maintained after controlling for the rest of microbial
357 attributed selected in the best model.

358 *Random Forest*

359 To further clarify the relative importance of bacterial richness and composition in predicting
360 multifunctionality, we conducted a classification Random Forest analysis (Breiman 2001), as done in
361 Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* (2015). Random Forest analysis for the field study includes as predictors:
362 bacterial richness, composition and total abundance, as well as latitude, longitude, soil carbon and pH.
363 Random Forest analyses for the experimental soils A and B include as predictors: bacterial richness,
364 composition and total abundance. This technique is a novel machine-learning algorithm that extends
365 standard classification and regression tree (CART) methods by creating a collection of classification
366 trees with binary divisions. Unlike traditional CART analyses, the fit of each tree is assessed using
367 randomly selected cases (1/3 of the data), which are withheld during its construction (out-of-bag or
368 OOB cases). The importance of each predictor variable is determined by evaluating the decrease in
369 prediction accuracy (i.e. increase in the mean square error between observations and OOB predictions)

370 when the data for that predictor is randomly permuted. This decrease is averaged over all trees to
371 produce the final measure of importance. These analyses were conducted using the rfPermute package
372 (Archer et al. 2016) of the R statistical software (<http://cran.r-project.org/>).

373

374 **Results**

375 *Field survey*

376 Our distance-based multi-modeling approach indicated that bacterial richness and composition (relative
377 abundance of β -Proteobacteria, γ -Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes and Actinobacteria) provided
378 independent and complementary information to predict multifunctionality (Table 1). The best-fitting
379 model accounted for over 60% of the variation in multifunctionality; and always included both bacterial
380 richness and composition as predictor variables (Table 1). Model fit declined substantially when we
381 removed either bacterial richness or composition as a predictor variable (Table 1; $\Delta\text{AICc} > 2$ threshold),
382 suggesting that both microbial components are important predictors of ecosystem multifunctionality.
383 Specifically, the same models with composition but without bacterial richness had a significantly but
384 modestly higher AICc than the best models including taxa richness and composition (ΔAICc of +2.23).
385 Models including only bacterial richness had a markedly higher ΔAICc (+23.11) than the best-fitting
386 model (Table 1). We then calculated the relative importance of all microbial attributes in predicting
387 multifunctionality using weighted information from all models. Bacterial richness was the fourth most
388 important predictor of multifunctionality after the relative abundance of Actinobacteria,
389 Gammaproteobacteria and Bacteroidetes (Fig. 1).

390 Our results remained unchanged even when we additionally included spatial (latitude and
391 longitude) and soil properties (soil carbon and pH; Table S5). Most importantly, our main result, that
392 bacterial richness and composition perform independently to drive multifunctionality, was maintained
393 after including in our model spatial influence, soil properties, bacterial richness, and bacterial
394 composition at the OTU level (three axes of a non-metric multidimensional scaling analysis [NMDS])
395 (Table S6). Note that the 3D solution of this NMDS had a very low stress (0.05) indicating that the
396 three axes of our NMDS were a good representation of the entire soil bacterial community in our Field
397 survey. Random Forest analyses provided further evidence that bacterial richness and composition were
398 significant predictors of multifunctionality after accounting for multiple multifunctionality drivers. Soil
399 C and pH were the major predictors of multifunctionality followed by microbial composition and
400 richness (Fig. S3).

401 Bacterial richness was positively related to multifunctionality (Fig. 2a), a result which remains
402 consistent after controlling for latitude and longitude (Table S7), total bacterial abundance (Table S8)
403 and the relative abundance of selected taxa in the best model (Table S9). These results were also
404 maintained when we explored the relationship between bacterial richness and the number of functions
405 at or above 25, 50 and 75% thresholds of the maximum observed function (Table S10). Moreover, we
406 found positive effects of bacterial richness on some individual functions (enzyme activities and carbon
407 degradation assays; Tables 2 and S11). For example, we found positive correlations (Spearman)
408 between bacterial richness and β -glucosidase ($P=0.01$), N-Acetylglucosaminidase ($P=0.08$) and SIR
409 Glucose ($P<0.01$) (Tables 2 and S11). Similar results were obtained when we evaluated the linear
410 relationships among bacterial richness and single functions, with cellobiosidase, but not N-
411 Acetylglucosaminidase, being positively related to bacterial richness in these analyses (Fig. S4).

412 Together, the selected bacterial phyla/classes Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes, α -, β -, γ -
413 Proteobacteria and Fimicutes accounted for 28-74% (average 53%) of the relative abundance of
414 bacteria from all sites. The relative abundance of Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes, β -Proteobacteria and γ -
415 Protobacteria were positively related to multifunctionality (Table 3). Regarding single functions, γ -
416 Proteobacteria was strongly related to phosphatase activity and basal respiration (Tables 2 and S11).
417 Conversely, Bacteroidetes, β -Proteobacteria and γ -Proteobacteria were positively related to most soil
418 functions in our Field survey.

419 *Microcosm study (Experimental approach)*

420 Supporting the results from our Field survey, our distance-based multi-modeling approach indicated
421 that bacterial richness and composition (relative abundance of Bacteroidetes and Actinobacteria for Soil
422 A and γ -Proteobacteria for Soil B) provided independent and complementary information to predict
423 multifunctionality (Table 1). The best-fitting models accounted for significant but modest (8% for soil
424 A) and substantial (43% for Soil B) percentages of the variation in multifunctionality for the two soils;
425 and always included both bacterial richness and composition as predictor variables (Table 1). Also,
426 similar to the results found for our Field survey, model fit declined substantially when we removed
427 either bacterial richness or composition as a predictor variable (Table 1; $\Delta AICc > 2$ threshold),
428 providing evidence that both microbial components are important predictors of ecosystem
429 multifunctionality. Specifically, the same models with composition but without bacterial richness had a
430 higher AICc than the best models including taxa richness and composition for Soil A (+26.69) and Soil
431 B (+12.84). Similarly, models including only bacterial richness had a higher $\Delta AICc$ for Soil A (+67.35)

432 and Soil B (+3.10). Mean values for multifunctionality in each of the 68 experimental microbial
433 combinations for soils A and B are available in Fig. S5.

434 Although models including both bacterial richness and composition always improved
435 multifunctionality predictions (vs. those models lacking one of these components; Table 1), our results
436 for the Microcosm study also suggested that the relative importance of bacterial richness compared
437 with composition is soil-dependent. Thus, richness was more important than composition in Soil B,
438 while the opposite pattern was observed for Soil A (Table 1). Similar results are found when we
439 calculated the relative importance of bacterial richness and composition using weighted information
440 from all models (Fig. 1). Alternatively, our Random Forest model indicated that bacterial richness was
441 the most important predictor of multifunctionality, but only after the relative abundance of
442 Actinobacteria for soil A and Gammaproteobacteria for soil B (Fig. S3).

443 Moreover, our Microcosm study provided evidence that the identity of the most relevant
444 microbial taxa is also soil-dependent. Thus, while Bacteroidetes and Actinobacteria were the strongest
445 predictors for Soil A (Table 1; Fig. 1), γ -Proteobacteria was the main predictor of multifunctionality in
446 Soil B (Table 1; Fig. 1). Interestingly, observational data from these two samples were consistent with
447 what we observed in our Microcosm study. Thus, the models based on the Field survey included the
448 main bacterial taxa in both soils from the Microcosm study and included β -Proteobacteria, γ -
449 Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes and Actinobacteria in the best models (Table 1).

450 We found the highest multifunctionality in the soil microcosms with the highest bacterial
451 richness in both Soils A and B (Figs. 2b and c; $P < 0.01$). These results remained consistent after
452 statistically controlling for total bacterial abundance (Tables S8 and S12; Fig. S6). In addition, the
453 positive effect of bacterial richness on multifunctionality was maintained after we removed key taxa
454 from the analyses, demonstrating that this effect was not just due to key taxa (sampling effect) (Fig.
455 S7). These results were also maintained when we explored the relationship between bacterial richness
456 and the number of functions at or above 25, 50 and 75% thresholds of the maximum observed function
457 (Table S10) and also after controlling for the relative abundance of selected taxa in the best model
458 (Table S9). For single functions, bacterial richness was positively related to N-Acetylglucosaminidase
459 and phosphatase activities in both soils from our Microcosm study and to β -glucosidase and
460 cellobiosidase activities in Soil A ($P < 0.05$; Tables 2 and S11 and Figs. S8 and S9).

461 In the Microcosm study, bacterial composition effects on multifunctionality were soil dependent
462 (see Fig. S10 for original bacterial composition in “soils A and B”), with a positive correlation between

463 multifunctionality and Actinobacteria and Bacteroidetes and a negative correlation with β -
464 Proteobacteria in soil A (Table 3), while in Soil B there was a positive correlation of multifunctionality
465 and γ -Proteobacteria. Similar results were found when we explored the relationship between bacterial
466 composition and the number of functions at or above 25, 50 and 75% thresholds of the maximum
467 observed function (Table S10). Consistent with these findings, the highest multifunctionality in the
468 diverse communities and the monocultures (i.e. bacterial taxa identity effects based on
469 presence/absence analyses) was found for Actinobacteria and Bacteroidetes in Soil A and
470 Proteobacteria classes in Soil B (Fig. 3; $P < 0.01$).

471 Moreover, the effects of bacterial composition on individual functions were also soil dependent
472 (Tables 2 and S11). For example, γ -Proteobacteria, which was strongly related to phosphatase activity
473 and basal respiration in Field survey (Tables 2 and S11), had a predominant positive effect on soil
474 functions from Soil B including N-Acetylglucosaminidase, basal respiration and SIR glucose and lignin
475 (Tables 2 and S11). Conversely, Actinobacteria and Bacteroidetes, which were positively related to a
476 wide array of functions in the Field survey, showed predominantly positive effects on functions in Soil
477 A including β -glucosidase, cellobiosidase and N-Acetylglucosaminidase, but also phosphatase and SIR
478 Lignin in particular case of the isolated bacteria from the phylum Actinobacteria (Tables 2 and S11).

479

480 **Discussion**

481 Despite the growing body of literature providing evidence that microbial diversity promotes ecosystem
482 functioning in terrestrial ecosystems (Jing *et al.* 2015; Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* 2016), most studies
483 have tended to focus on a particular component of diversity (richness or composition), and no previous
484 study, to the best of our knowledge, has empirically and statistically examined the relative importance
485 of both bacterial richness and composition in supporting multiple functions in terrestrial ecosystems.
486 Using observational and experimental data, we provide evidence that both bacterial richness and
487 composition are key drivers of multiple ecosystems functions in terrestrial ecosystems. Most
488 importantly, our multi-model approach indicates that these two microbial diversity components provide
489 independent and complementary information on the role of bacteria in ecosystem processes. These
490 results provide strong support for the hypothesis that the effects of bacterial biodiversity on ecosystem
491 functioning are due to the combined effects of bacterial richness and identity of key taxa within a
492 community. Ours is, to our knowledge, the first attempt to evaluate the relative importance of both
493 diversity and composition of bacteria, the most diverse and abundant organisms on Earth, in driving

494 multifunctionality. However, future studies exploring the relative importance of microbial drivers of
495 multifunctionality should be encouraged to include diversity and composition of fungi to obtain a
496 broader picture of the role of microbial diversity and composition in driving multifunctionality.

497 Both our field survey and microcosm study provide evidence that bacterial richness is strongly
498 positively related to multifunctionality. Our results were maintained after controlling for spatial
499 structure (in observational data) and microbial abundance using partial correlations and ANCOVA
500 analyses, and provided experimental support to previous observational studies showing positive
501 relationships between soil microbial diversity and multiple soil functions, such as those used here (He
502 *et al.* 2009; Jing *et al.* 2015; Delgado-Baquerizo *et al.* 2016). The mechanisms behind the positive
503 effects of bacterial richness on multifunctionality could include an increase in the interactions among
504 microbial taxa (complementarity effects; Loreau & Hector 2001) and the so-called “sampling effect”
505 (i.e. increasing taxa richness increases the likelihood that key taxa would be present; Hooper *et al.*
506 2005). Species interactions are especially important for microbial communities that rely heavily on
507 aggregated processes (Schimel *et al.* 2005) such as organic matter decomposition as an energy source.
508 These aggregated processes involve many metabolic routes and require the cooperation of large and
509 diverse groups of microbes to break down complex and recalcitrant polymers into simpler, more labile
510 monomers, which are rapidly consumed and largely respired (Schimel *et al.* 2005). Thus, losses in
511 bacterial richness may inactivate critical functions (e.g. chitin degradation), but also can reduce the
512 rates in which multiple ecosystems functions are being produced, as supported by our observational and
513 experimental data. Bacterial richness also showed similar positive trends with each of the single
514 functions studied. Of particular interest was the fact that bacterial richness showed a strong and positive
515 effect on N-Acetylglucosaminidase (chitinase) in all the experimental approaches used here. Chitin is
516 an extremely complex compound, is a structural component of many organisms, and is widespread in
517 nature (Beier & Bertilsson 2013). Bacteria are believed to be major mediators of chitin degradation, a
518 complex process that involves several metabolic reactions with important implications for carbon and
519 nitrogen cycling (Beier & Bertilsson 2013). This result further supports the notion that complex
520 processes such as organic matter decomposition are favored by the existence of a diverse collection of
521 microbes all contributing to the overall process to promote the highest degradation rates (Schimel *et al.*
522 2005). Our Microcosm study also showed that a “sampling effect” may be, at least in part, responsible
523 for driving multifunctionality, as microcosms including certain key taxa tended to have the greatest
524 multifunctionality. Interestingly, bacterial richness had a positive effect on multifunctionality even after

525 the effects of key species were accounted for (removing them) in our analyses (Fig. S6; Appendix S1).
526 Consistent with the results reported by Hooper *et al.* (2005) for plant communities, we suggest that
527 microbial taxa interaction and sampling effects are not mutually exclusive.

528 Bacterial composition was also a strong predictor of multifunctionality in both Field and
529 Microcosm studies. However, unlike bacterial richness, the effects of bacterial composition on
530 multifunctionality varied with both soil properties and ecological characteristics of the specific bacterial
531 taxa, especially under the Microcosm study. For example, for Soil B (high soil carbon), γ -
532 Proteobacteria enhanced multifunctionality in both single and mixed cultures. Similarly, γ -
533 Proteobacteria, which was positively related to soil carbon (Table S13), also showed a positive
534 relationship with multifunctionality across the Field survey. Class γ -Proteobacteria tend to exhibit
535 copiotrophic life histories (Fierer *et al.* 2007; Trivedi *et al.* 2013), preferring environments that are rich
536 in carbon, promoting the greatest multifunctionality and supporting critical processes such as complex
537 and labile carbon decomposition. Thus, this Proteobacteria class may be critical for supporting
538 multifunctionality in carbon-rich soils. Conversely, for Soil A (lowest soil carbon) in the Microcosm
539 study, we found a predominant effect of Actinobacteria in supporting multifunctionality. Actinobacteria
540 are defined as oligotrophs (Bastian *et al.* 2009; Trivedi *et al.* 2013), and are more competitive in soils
541 with low levels of carbon such as those from drylands (Maestre *et al.* 2015). In Soil A, Actinobacteria
542 was also strongly positively related to extracellular enzyme activity and lignin degradation content. Our
543 findings are supported by the results of previous studies suggesting that Actinobacteria contains a broad
544 array of genes that allow the breakdown and utilization of recalcitrant organic compounds such as
545 lignin, chitin and cellulose that can be used under stressful soil conditions (low carbon; Bastian *et al.*
546 2009; Trivedi *et al.* 2013).

547 Interestingly, only the relative abundance of Bacteroidetes was consistently selected as a major
548 predictor of multifunctionality in all experimental approaches and statistical models used here. In
549 general, the relative abundance of Bacteroidetes, defined as copiotrophic organism by Fierer *et al.*
550 (2007), promoted high rates of multifunctionality, enzyme activities and/or respiration rates in all
551 experimental approaches (Table 2). More specifically, the relative abundance of Bacteroidetes always
552 promoted the activity of chitin degradation in all soils. These results are in agreement with a previous
553 study highlighting their potential to break down chitin and cellulose in terrestrial ecosystems (Trivedi *et*
554 *al.* 2013); and further highlight the importance of this taxa in regulating organic matter decomposition
555 and C cycling in soil.

556 An important finding of our study is that although both components of biodiversity are
557 important drivers of multiple ecosystem processes related to organic matter decomposition and nutrient
558 cycling, the relative importance of richness compared with composition in controlling
559 multifunctionality is soil-dependent, as supported by our Microcosm study (Soil A vs. B). In particular,
560 we found that richness is more important than composition in Soil B, with the higher soil organic
561 matter, while the opposite pattern occurred in Soil A. Although we cannot extrapolate from only two
562 soils, if these results were generally true, they would suggest that bacterial richness might play a
563 predominant role in organic soils, where the interaction among multiple microbial communities is
564 needed to break down complex and recalcitrant polymers into simpler and more labile monomers
565 (organic matter degradation; Schimel *et al.* 2005). Conversely, species identity (Bacteroidetes and
566 Actinobacteria in Soil A) may play a major role in mineral soils. For instance, Actinobacteria have been
567 shown to possess important adaptations that enable them to resist environmental harshness (ability to
568 survive desiccation and low nutrient availability conditions; Battistuzzi & Hedges 2009). Thus, these
569 results support the notion that both microbial richness and composition are needed to accurately
570 estimate the consequences of losses in microbial diversity (from global environmental changes such as
571 climate change and land use intensification) on ecosystem functioning.

572 Interestingly, observational data were consistent with what we observed in our Microcosm
573 study, providing insights into the main microbial pattern controlling multifunctionality in terrestrial
574 ecosystems, and demonstrating the value of using each of these approaches. For example, in both the
575 field and microcosm studies, an increase in taxa richness was positively related to multifunctionality.
576 Of particular novelty, the Field data provided a comprehensive view of the main taxa controlling
577 multifunctionality in Soils A and B and suggest that Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes and γ -Proteobacteria
578 are the main drivers of multifunctionality in terrestrial ecosystems at a large scale. All of these bacterial
579 taxa are globally distributed and dominant in many terrestrial ecosystems worldwide (Fierer *et al.* 2009;
580 Maestre *et al.* 2015). This result suggests that observational data can be useful for predicting microbial
581 community shifts and their consequences for ecosystem functioning under global change, but also that
582 this observational data will be useful in developing generic algorithms to be included in global
583 biogeochemical models.

584 In conclusion, our findings provide strong evidence, from two independent approaches, that
585 bacterial richness and composition are important, yet independent drivers of multiple ecosystem
586 functions related to organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling. Greater microbial richness and

587 globally-dominant bacterial taxa such as γ -Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria and Bacteroidetes were
588 critical drivers of multifunctionality in both our field and microcosm studies. Information on both
589 microbial richness and composition therefore need to be considered when formulating sustainable
590 management and conservation policies, and when predicting the effects of global change on ecosystem
591 functions. These findings advance our understanding of the mechanisms underpinning relationships
592 between biodiversity and ecosystem functionality in terrestrial ecosystems, and reinforce the need to
593 develop approaches and policies to protect soil microbial diversity and their positive effects for
594 multiple ecosystems functions.

595 **Conflict of Interest**

596 The authors declare no competing financial interests.

597 **Author's contributions**

598 M.D-B. conceived the idea of this study and designed experiments in consultation with B.K.S., P.B.R.
599 and P.T. Soil sampling was conducted by M.D-B. and D.J.E. Laboratory analyses were done by M.D-
600 B., P.T. and C.T. Bioinformatics analyses were done by T.C.J. Statistical modeling was conducted by
601 M.D-B. The manuscript was written by M.D-B with contributions from all co-authors.

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609 **Data accessibility.**

610 The primary data used in this study is available in Table S1.

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Figure 1. Relative importance of bacterial richness and composition in models of multifunctionality for the field (a) and experimental studies (b-c). The height of each bar is the sum of the Akaike weights of all models that included the predictor of interest, taking into account the number of models in which each predictor appears.

746

747 **Figure 2.** Effects of bacterial richness on multifunctionality for Field (a) and Microcosm (b and c)
 748 studies. Bacterial diversity in Field survey is calculated as the number of OTUs (97% similarity; χ^2 -
 749 transformed). Bacterial diversity in the Microcosm study (“soil A and B”) is the number of bacterial
 750 phyla/classes. The solid lines in figure a represents the fitted linear regression. Data in Fig b (Soil A)
 751 and c (Soil B) represent means \pm SE. Different letters in panels b) and c) indicate significant differences
 752 between richness levels ($P < 0.005$) in multifunctionality index (*post-hoc* tests after one-way ANOVA).

753

754 **Figure 3.** Mean (\pm SE) values for multifunctionality across different bacterial taxa for mono- (a and c)
 755 and mixed cultures (b and d) of bacteria in the experimental approach. Different letters in panels a) and
 756 c) indicate significant differences in multifunctionality among bacterial taxa ($P < 0.05$) as tested using
 757 post-hoc tests after one-way ANOVA. Panels b) and d) represent averaging multifunctionality index in
 758 mixed cultures including (presence) or excluding (absence) each bacterial phylum/class. In these panels
 759 significance levels are as follows: ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

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765 **Table 1.** Best-fitting model (including microbial richness and composition) and the same model with
766 either bacterial richness or composition (but not both) included as predictors of multifunctionality for
767 the Field and Microcosm (“soils A and B”) studies. Shaded cells indicate that the variable has been
768 included in the model. Models are ranked by AICc. AICc measures the relative goodness of fit of a
769 given model; the lower its value, the more likely the model to be correct. Δ AICc is the difference
770 between the AICc of each model and that of the best model. Δ AICc indicates substantially different
771 models. A = α -Proteobacteria; B = β -Proteobacteria; C = γ -Proteobacteria; D = Firmicutes; E =
772 Bacteroidetes; F = Actinobacteria.
773

Approach	Diversity	Composition	R ²	AICc	Δ AICc
I (Field study)	Richness	γ -Proteobacteria + Firmicutes + Bacteroidetes+ Actinobacteria	0.599	-53.75	0.00
	Excluded	γ -Proteobacteria + Firmicutes + Bacteroidetes+ Actinobacteria	0.551	-51.52	2.23
	Richness	Excluded	0.134	-30.64	23.11
II (Soil A)	Richness	Bacteroidetes+ Actinobacteria	0.429	-445.74	0.00
	Excluded	Bacteroidetes+ Actinobacteria	0.344	-419.05	26.69
	Richness	Excluded	0.190	-378.39	67.35
II (Soil B)	Richness	γ -Proteobacteria	0.084	-276.88	0.00
	Excluded	γ -Proteobacteria	0.014	-264.04	12.84
	Richness	Excluded	0.060	-273.78	3.10

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788 **Table 2.** Summary of the effects of microbial composition on the multiple ecosystems functions in this
789 study for the field and microcosm (soils A and B) studies. Microbial composition effects are based on
790 Spearman correlations available in Table S7. Symbols + and - indicate positive and negative
791 interactions.

Study	Functions	Richness	α - Proteobacteria	β - Proteobacteria	γ - Proteobacteria	Firmicutes	Bacteroidetes	Actinobacteria
Field	β -Glucosidase	+		+	+		+	+
	Cellobiosidase			+	+		+	
	N- Acetylglucosaminidase	+		+	+		+	
	Phosphatase		+	+	+			
	Basal Respiration		+	+	+		+	+
	SIR Glucose	+		+			+	+
	SIR Lignin			+	+		+	
	Microcosm (Soil A)	β -Glucosidase	+		-	-		+
Cellobiosidase		+					+	+
N- Acetylglucosaminidase		+		-	-		+	+
Phosphatase		+						+
Basal Respiration		-		-	+			
SIR Glucose				+				
SIR Lignin			-		-	+		+
Microcosm (Soil B)		β -Glucosidase						
	Cellobiosidase							
	N- Acetylglucosaminidase	+			+	+	+	
	Phosphatase	+						+
	Basal Respiration			-	+	-		
	SIR Glucose				+	-		
	SIR Lignin				+	-		

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800 **Table 3.** Correlations (Spearman) between main bacteria taxa and multifunctionality for field and M
 801 microcosm (soils A and B) studies (n = 204). *P*-values are in brackets.
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Study	α - Proteobacteria	β - Proteobacteria	γ - Proteobacteria	Firmicutes	Bacteroidetes	Actinobacteria
Field	0.111 (0.480)	0.570 (<0.001)	0.566 (<0.001)	-0.007 (0.963)	0.637 (<0.001)	0.291 (0.058)
Microcosm (Soil A)	-0.036 (0.612)	-0.153 (0.029)	-0.108 (0.124)	-0.080 (0.257)	0.297 (<0.001)	0.532 (<0.001)
Microcosm (Soil B)	-0.003 (0.964)	0.074 (0.294)	0.223 (0.001)	-0.050 (0.474)	0.021 (0.764)	0.082 (0.244)

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828 **Supplementary Information**

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830 **Microbial richness and composition independently drive soil multifunctionality**

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832 Manuel Delgado-Baquerizo, Pankaj Trivedi, Chanda Trivedi, David J. Eldridge, Peter B. Reich,
833 Thomas C. Jeffries, Brajesh K. Singh.

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837 **This PDF file includes:**

838 Appendix S1

839 Tables S1-13

840 Figures S1-10

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856 **Appendix S1. Supplementary Methods.**

857 Soil sterilization (Microcosm study)

858 One week after the initial sterilization the soil samples received a second cycle of gamma radiation (50
859 kGy) to ensure the minimum survival of fungal spores. We used gamma radiation because it is known
860 to cause minimal change to the physical properties of soils compared with other methods such as soil
861 autoclaving (Wolf *et al.* 1989; Lotrario *et al.* 1995). We further verified the efficiency of sterilization by
862 serially diluting soils samples in nutrient medium (for composition see below). No growth was
863 observed after 5 days of incubation at 28 °C.

864 Microbial isolation.

865 Bacterial strains from six terrestrial dominant phylogenetic taxa belonged to phylum Actinobacteria
866 (*Streptomyces* spp.), Firmicutes (*Bacillus* spp.), Bacteroidetes (*Chryseobacterium* spp.), and
867 Proteobacteria classes α -Proteobacteria (*Ensifer* spp.), β -Proteobacteria (*Burkholderia* spp.), and γ -
868 Proteobacteria (*Pseudomonas* spp.) (Fig. S2), were isolated across both “soils A and B”. The
869 identification of the bacterial isolates was performed using full-length 16S rDNA sequencing. Bacterial
870 cultures were kept in glycerol stocks at -80 °C and grown in nutrient medium (peptic digest of animal
871 tissue 1.5 g l⁻¹, yeast extract 1.5 g l⁻¹, sodium chloride 5 g l⁻¹, beef extract 1.5 g l⁻¹ each from DIFCO
872 laboratories, USA). A single colony of each bacterial culture was picked, grown overnight (24 h for
873 Actinobacteria) in nutrient broth, washed in phosphate buffered saline and adjusted to an OD₆₀₀ of
874 0.001 (equivalent to 10⁸ cells of bacteria). Bacterial cultures were left for 6 h at room temperature
875 before assembling the communities. To ensure this number of cells, we also checked for their
876 abundance using quantitative PCR (qPCR) approaches (see qPCR details below), before soil
877 inoculation.

878 Molecular analyses.

879 *Field study.* Initial sequence processing and diversity analyses were conducted using the QIIME
880 package (Caporaso *et al.* 2010). Initially, low quality regions (Q<20) were trimmed from the 5' end of
881 sequences and paired ends were joined with FLASH (Magoč & Salzberg 2011). Sequences were de-
882 multiplexed and a further round of quality control was conducted to remove sequences containing
883 ambiguous bases (N), and reads containing bases with a quality score below 25. Chimeric 16S rDNA
884 sequences were detected using the UCHIME algorithm from the USEARCH package (Edgar 2010;
885 Edgar *et al.* 2011) implemented within VSEARCH (<https://github.com/torognes/vsearch>). The RDP
886 training dataset V950 was used as a reference for chimera detection, as recommended by the UCHIME
887 documentation. The remaining high quality chimera free sequences were used for downstream analysis.
888 Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) were defined as clusters of 97% sequence similarity using

889 UCLUST (Edgar 2010). Taxonomy was assigned using UCLUST against the Greengenes database
890 version 13_85 (DeSantis *et al.* 2006; McDonald *et al.* 2012) for 16S rDNA OTUs. The resultant OTU
891 abundance tables were filtered to remove singletons and rarefied to an even number of sequences per
892 samples to ensure an equal sampling depth (11925 sequences). We used species richness from next
893 generation sequencing (i.e. number of OTUs at 97% similarity) as a proxy of diversity as it is likely to
894 be the most compatible approach to the one used in our experimental design (i.e. number of taxa). The
895 number of bacterial sequences obtained from one of the soil samples surveyed was too low to estimate
896 microbial diversity accurately, so that sample was not used in further analyses, which left remaining a
897 total of 43 soil samples.

898 *Microcosm study.* To check whether the original composition assigned to the different microcosms was
899 maintained by the end of the experiment and take into account changes in bacterial yield in our
900 microcosms, we quantified the abundance of each of the selected phyla/classes with qPCR and
901 Actino235/Eub518, Cfb319/Eub518, Eub338/Alf685, Eub338/Bet680, Gamma395f/Gamma871r and
902 Lgc353/Eub518 primer sets for Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes and α -, β - and γ -Proteobacteria and
903 Firmicutes, respectively (Fierer *et al.* 2005; Philippot *et al.* 2010). The abundance of all qPCR genes
904 was expressed as the number of DNA copies per gram of dry soil. To obtain these units, we first
905 calculated the number of DNA copies per ng of DNA in our PCR reaction. Then, we obtained the
906 number of DNA copies in our whole DNA extraction (100 μ l). Finally, we obtained the number of DNA
907 copies per gram of dry soil. Using these data, we calculated the corrected relative abundance of each
908 phylum/class per microcosm.

909 Statistical analyses.

910 *Considering sampling effects on our analyses.*

911 Finally, drawing upon the results included in Fig. 2a and b, and to account for sampling effects (i.e.
912 increasing taxa richness increases the likelihood that those key taxa would be present, we repeated our
913 ANCOVA analyses to explore whether the effects of richness on multifunctionality are still maintained
914 for the less functional taxa, after removing key taxa (i.e. those taxa that had an outstanding effect in
915 controlling multifunctionality in monospecific and mixed cultures and the observational gradient).
916 Separate analyses were conducted for “soils A and B”.

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919 **Figure S1.** Locations of the 22 study sites in this study including Field and Microcosm (soils A and B)

920 studies.

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Figure S2. Information of bacterial strains used in the study.

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972 **Figure S3.** Random Forest mean predictor importance (percentage of increase in mean square error) of
 973 bacterial richness, composition, total abundance and location and soil properties (i.e., for the
 974 observational study) on multifunctionality. ** $P < 0.01$; * $P \leq 0.05$.

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978 **Figure S4.** Linear regressions between bacterial diversity (number of phylotypes) and single functions

979 (n = 43). Bacterial richness is calculated as the number of OTUs (97% similarity; x^2 -transformed).

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993 **Figure S6.** Total abundance of bacteria (16s rRNA gene) for the different bacterial richness levels in
 994 the Microcosm study at the end of the incubation period (soils A and B).

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1013 **Figure S7.** Bacterial richness effects on multifunctionality after removing key species
 1014 (Bacteroidetes/Actinobacteria and Proteobacteria classes for soils A and B, respectively) in Field and
 1015 Microcosm (soils A and B) studies (see Appendix S1 – statistical analyses).

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1023 **Figure S8.** Effects of bacterial richness on single functions for our soil A from the experimental
 1024 approach. Bacterial diversity is the number of bacterial phyla/classes.

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1026 **Figure S9.** Effects of bacterial richness on single functions for our soil B from the experimental
 1027 approach. Bacterial diversity is the number of bacterial phyla/classes.

Figure S10. Relative abundance of main bacterial phyla in soils A and B used for the Microcosm study.

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1044 **Table S1.** Primary data used in this study including information on location, soil properties, bacterial
1045 richness, composition and total abundance.

1046 *Table S1 is available online as a Separate Excel file under the Supporting Information for this article.*

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1075 **Table S2.** Summary on the multiple microbial combinations used in this study including those for
 1076 species richness one, two, four and six. A = α -Proteobacteria; B = β -Proteobacteria; C = γ -
 1077 Proteobacteria; D = Firmicutes; E = Bacteroidetes; F = Actinobacteria.
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Diversity	Combination	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	A	100	0	0	0	0	0
1	B	0	100	0	0	0	0
1	C	0	0	100	0	0	0
1	D	0	0	0	100	0	0
1	E	0	0	0	0	100	0
1	F	0	0	0	0	0	100
2	AB	50	50	0	0	0	0
2	AC	50	0	50	0	0	0
2	AD	50	0	0	50	0	0
2	AE	50	0	0	0	50	0
2	AF	50	0	0	0	0	50
2	BC	0	50	50	0	0	0
2	BD	0	50	0	50	0	0
2	BE	0	50	0	0	50	0
2	BF	0	50	0	0	0	50
2	CD	0	0	50	50	0	0
2	CE	0	0	50	0	50	0
2	CF	0	0	50	0	0	50
2	DE	0	0	0	50	50	0
2	DF	0	0	0	50	0	50
2	EF	0	0	0	0	50	50
2	AB	25	75	0	0	0	0
2	AC	25	0	75	0	0	0
2	AD	25	0	0	75	0	0
2	AE	25	0	0	0	75	0
2	AF	25	0	0	0	0	75
2	BC	0	25	75	0	0	0
2	BD	0	25	0	75	0	0

2	BE	0	25	0	0	75	0
2	BF	0	25	0	0	0	75
2	CD	0	0	25	75	0	0
2	CE	0	0	25	0	75	0
2	CF	0	0	25	0	0	75
2	DE	0	0	0	25	75	0
2	DF	0	0	0	25	0	75
2	EF	0	0	0	0	25	75
2	AB	75	25	0	0	0	0
2	AC	75	0	25	0	0	0
2	AD	75	0	0	25	0	0
2	AE	75	0	0	0	25	0
2	AF	75	0	0	0	0	25
2	BC	0	75	25	0	0	0
2	BD	0	75	0	25	0	0
2	BE	0	75	0	0	25	0
2	BF	0	75	0	0	0	25
2	CD	0	0	75	25	0	0
2	CE	0	0	75	0	25	0
2	CF	0	0	75	0	0	25
2	DE	0	0	0	75	25	0
2	DF	0	0	0	75	0	25
2	EF	0	0	0	0	75	25
4	ABCD	25	25	25	25	0	0
4	ABCE	25	25	25	0	25	0
4	ABCF	25	25	25	0	0	25
4	ACDE	25	0	25	25	25	0
4	ACDF	25	0	25	25	0	25
4	ADEF	25	0	0	25	25	25
4	BCDE	0	25	25	25	25	0
4	BCDF	0	25	25	25	0	25
4	BDEF	0	25	0	25	25	25
4	CDEF	0	0	25	25	25	25
4	ABDE	25	25	0	25	25	0
4	ABDF	25	25	0	25	0	25
4	ABEF	25	25	0	0	25	25

4	ACEF	25	0	25	0	25	25
4	BCEF	0	25	25	0	25	25
6	ABCDEF	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6
6	ABCDEF	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6

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1107 **Table S3.** Correlations (Spearman) between averaging multifunctionality index (used in this study) and
1108 the number of functions at or above a threshold (25, 50 and 75%) of the maximum observed function (n
1109 = 43 for the Field study and n = 204 for each of the soils in the Microcosm study).

Approach	25%	50%	75%
I (Field study)	0.875	0.918	0.875
	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
II (Soil A)	0.783	0.886	0.596
	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
II (Soil B)	0.615	0.788	0.700
	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

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1137 **Table S4.** Correlations (Spearman) between bacterial richness and composition for Field (n = 43) and
 1138 Microcosm (soils A and B) studies (n = 204). n = number of samples. A = α -Proteobacteria; B = β -
 1139 Proteobacteria; C = γ -Proteobacteria; D = Firmicutes; E = Bacteroidetes; F = Actinobacteria.

Study	Parameter	A	B	C	D	E	F
Field	ρ	-0.442	0.495	0.023	0.332	0.536	0.138
	P-value	0.003	0.001	0.883	0.030	<0.001	0.376
Microcosm (Soil A)	ρ	0.213	0.232	0.212	0.216	0.228	0.264
	P-value	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001	<0.001
Microcosm (Soil B)	ρ	0.217	0.301	0.218	0.218	0.245	0.225
	P-value	0.002	<0.001	0.002	0.002	<0.001	0.001

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1167 **Table S5.** Best-fitting (including bacterial richness, composition, soil properties and/or spatial
 1168 variables) and same model with bacterial richness/composition (selected bacterial taxa included in this
 1169 study) only as predictors of multifunctionality for Field study. Shaded cells indicate that the variable
 1170 has been included in the model. Models are ranked by AICc. AICc measures the relative goodness of fit
 1171 of a given model; the lower its value, the more likely the model to be correct. Δ AICc are difference
 1172 between the AICc of each model and that of the best model. Δ AICc indicate substantially different
 1173 models. A = α -Proteobacteria; B = β -Proteobacteria; C = γ -Proteobacteria; D = Firmicutes; E =
 1174 Bacteroidetes; F = Actinobacteria.
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Approach	Diversity	Composition	Soil properties	Spatial	R ²	AICc	Δ AICc
I (Field study)	Richness		Soil C + pH		0.780	-79.60	0.00
	Excluded	Firmicutes + Bacteroidetes	Soil C + pH		0.708	-70.07	9.53
	Richness	Excluded	Soil C + pH		0.731	-76.15	3.45

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1194 **Table S6.** Best-fitting (including bacterial richness, composition, soil properties and/or spatial
 1195 variables) and same model with bacterial richness/composition (three axes of a NMDS including
 1196 microbial composition at the OTU level) only as predictors of multifunctionality for Field study.
 1197 Shaded cells indicate that the variable has been included in the model. Models are ranked by AICc.
 1198 AICc measures the relative goodness of fit of a given model; the lower its value, the more likely the
 1199 model to be correct. Δ AICc are difference between the AICc of each model and that of the best model.
 1200 Δ AICc indicate substantially different models.

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Approach	Diversity	Composition	Soil properties	Spatial	R ²	AICc	Δ AICc
I (Field study)	Richness	NMDS#3	Soil C + pH	Longitude	0.808	-85.37	0.00
	Excluded	NMDS#3	Soil C + pH	Longitude	0.633	-60.29	25.08
	Richness	Excluded	Soil C + pH	Longitude	0.765	-79.35	6.02

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1219 **Table S7.** Partial Correlations between bacterial richness (x^2 -transformed) and composition with
1220 multifunctionality controlling for latitude and longitude (n = 43). A = α -Proteobacteria; B = β -
1221 Proteobacteria; C = γ -Proteobacteria; D = Firmicutes; E = Bacteroidetes; F = Actinobacteria.
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Parameter	Richness	A	B	C	D	E	F
Pearson's r	0.370	0.098	0.482	0.504	-0.087	0.570	0.361
<i>P-value</i>	0.017	0.541	0.001	0.001	0.590	<0.001	0.021

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1248 **Table S8.** Partial Correlations between bacterial richness and composition with multifunctionality
 1249 controlling for total bacterial abundance (qPCR). A = α -Proteobacteria; B = β -Proteobacteria; C = γ -
 1250 Proteobacteria; D = Firmicutes; E = Bacteroidetes; F = Actinobacteria.

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Approach	Parameter	Richness	A	B	C	D	E	F
I	Pearson's r	0.335	-0.019	0.427	0.401	-0.105	0.484	0.490
	P-value	0.030	0.904	0.005	0.009	0.509	0.001	0.001
II (soil A)	Pearson's r	0.428	-0.235	-0.149	-0.197	-0.250	0.112	0.493
	P-value	<0.001	0.001	0.034	0.005	<0.001	0.110	<0.001
II (soil B)	Pearson's r	0.250	-0.075	0.024	0.118	-0.076	0.100	-0.087
	P-value	<0.001	0.288	0.730	0.094	0.283	0.154	0.215

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1271 **Table S9.** Partial Correlations between bacterial richness and composition with multifunctionality
 1272 controlling for either bacterial richness and/or composition for the Field and Microcosm (“soils A and
 1273 B”) studies.
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Study	Microbial attribute	Controlled for	r	P-value
Field study	Bacterial richness	Gammaproteobacteria + Firmicutes+ Bacteroidetes+ Actinobacteria	0.329	0.041
		Bacterial richness + Firmicutes+ Bacteroidetes+ Actinobacteria	0.402	0.011
	Gammaproteobacteria	Gammaproteobacteria + Bacterial richness + Bacteroidetes+ Actinobacteria	-0.28	0.085
	Firmicutes	Gammaproteobacteria + Firmicutes+ Bacterial richness + Actinobacteria	0.352	0.028
	Bacteroidetes	Gammaproteobacteria + Firmicutes+ Bacteroidetes+ Bacterial richness	0.521	0.001
	Actinobacteria	Bacteroidetes+ Actinobacteria	0.362	<0.001
Soil A	Bacterial richness	Bacterial richness + Actinobacteria	0.388	<0.001
	Bacteroidetes	Bacteroidetes+ Bacterial richness	0.52	<0.001
	Actinobacteria	Bacterial richness	0.52	<0.001
Soil B	Bacterial richness	Gammaproteobacteria	0.266	<0.001
	Gammaproteobacteria	Bacterial richness	0.158	0.024

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1282 **Table S10.** Correlations (Spearman) between the richness and composition of bacteria and the number
 1283 of functions at or above a threshold (25, 50 and 75%) of the maximum observed function (n = 43 for
 1284 the Field study and n = 204 for each of the soils in the Microcosm study).

Approach	Number of Functions beyond thresholds	Parameter	Richness	A	B	C	D	E	F
I (Field study)	25%	ρ	0.334	0.149	0.571	0.462	0.071	0.587	0.340
		P-value	0.029	0.341	<0.001	0.002	0.652	<0.001	0.026
	50%	ρ	0.319	0.092	0.574	0.538	-0.012	0.570	0.242
		P-value	0.037	0.558	<0.001	<0.001	0.940	<0.001	0.118
	75%	ρ	0.346	0.084	0.538	0.572	-0.009	0.580	0.235
		P-value	0.023	0.593	<0.001	<0.001	0.952	<0.001	0.129
II (Soil A)	25%	ρ	0.448	-0.046	-0.189	-0.036	0.006	0.383	0.358
		P-value	<0.001	0.509	0.007	0.609	0.935	<0.001	<0.001
	50%	ρ	0.365	0.001	-0.220	-0.100	-0.092	0.322	0.436
		P-value	<0.001	0.995	0.002	0.156	0.189	<0.001	<0.001
	75%	ρ	0.217	-0.021	-0.004	-0.151	-0.067	0.026	0.445
		P-value	0.002	0.770	0.951	0.031	0.342	0.709	<0.001
II (Soil B)	25%	ρ	0.146	-0.083	-0.020	0.237	-0.005	-0.013	0.099
		P-value	0.037	0.239	0.774	0.001	0.945	0.856	0.160
	50%	ρ	0.087	-0.047	0.150	0.065	-0.012	-0.002	0.082
		P-value	0.217	0.506	0.033	0.356	0.866	0.980	0.245
	75%	ρ	0.123	0.058	0.056	0.207	-0.098	-0.018	0.078
		P-value	0.080	0.406	0.428	0.003	0.161	0.793	0.266

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1293 **Table S11.** Correlations (Spearman) between microbial composition and each of the single functions
 1294 included in this study for Field and Microcosm (soils A and B) studies. A = α -Proteobacteria; B = β -
 1295 Proteobacteria; C = γ -Proteobacteria; D = Firmicutes; E = Bacteroidetes; F = Actinobacteria.

Approach	Function	Parameter	Richness	A	B	C	D	E	F	
I	β-Glucosidase	ρ	0.396	-0.100	0.372	0.288	0.053	0.443	0.308	
		P-value	0.009	0.523	0.014	0.061	0.736	0.003	0.045	
	Cellobiosidase	ρ	0.254	0.012	0.351	0.396	0.024	0.434	0.203	
		P-value	0.100	0.939	0.021	0.009	0.880	0.004	0.192	
	N-Acetylglucosaminidase	ρ	0.267	0.164	0.475	0.542	-0.048	0.496	0.211	
		P-value	0.083	0.293	0.001	<0.001	0.759	0.001	0.174	
	Phosphatase	ρ	0.103	0.341	0.391	0.599	-0.051	0.231	-0.002	
		P-value	0.511	0.025	0.010	<0.001	0.748	0.136	0.988	
	Basal Respiration	ρ	0.205	0.336	0.549	0.722	-0.106	0.548	0.293	
		P-value	0.188	0.028	<0.001	<0.001	0.498	<0.001	0.056	
	SIR Glucose	ρ	0.577	-0.198	0.537	0.205	0.107	0.593	0.283	
		P-value	<0.001	0.203	<0.001	0.187	0.495	<0.001	0.066	
	SIR Lignin	ρ	0.237	-0.110	0.363	0.271	0.021	0.429	0.245	
		P-value	0.127	0.481	0.017	0.079	0.892	0.004	0.114	
	II (Soil A)	β-Glucosidase	ρ	0.260	-0.002	-0.315	-0.122	-0.155	0.291	0.468
			P-value	<0.001	0.982	<0.001	0.081	0.027	<0.001	<0.001
Cellobiosidase		ρ	0.522	0.107	-0.108	-0.015	-0.081	0.353	0.321	
		P-value	<0.001	0.128	0.123	0.836	0.250	<0.001	<0.001	
N-Acetylglucosaminidase		ρ	0.347	-0.095	-0.305	-0.157	-0.081	0.330	0.577	
		P-value	<0.001	0.178	<0.001	0.025	0.250	<0.001	<0.001	
Phosphatase		ρ	0.289	0.063	0.094	-0.109	-0.009	0.012	0.340	
		P-value	<0.001	0.373	0.182	0.121	0.899	0.865	<0.001	
Basal Respiration		ρ	-0.154	-0.098	-0.162	0.145	-0.020	-0.106	-0.017	
		P-value	0.027	0.163	0.020	0.039	0.774	0.133	0.805	
SIR Glucose		ρ	0.038	-0.043	0.117	0.030	0.031	-0.008	-0.055	
		P-value	0.594	0.542	0.097	0.670	0.657	0.915	0.436	
SIR Lignin		ρ	0.045	-0.137	0.075	-0.155	0.120	0.044	0.149	
		P-value	0.525	0.051	0.287	0.027	0.086	0.533	0.034	
II (Soil B)		β-Glucosidase	ρ	0.053	-0.109	0.082	0.048	0.072	-0.031	0.103
			P-value	0.452	0.122	0.244	0.495	0.306	0.655	0.143
	Cellobiosidase	ρ	0.084	0.025	0.026	0.059	0.038	-0.041	-0.044	
		P-value	0.235	0.721	0.717	0.402	0.589	0.556	0.531	
	N-	ρ	0.325	-0.111	0.104	0.191	0.169	0.124	-0.018	

Acetylglucosaminidase								
	P-value	<0.001	0.113	0.140	0.006	0.016	0.078	0.798
Phosphatase	ρ	0.259	-0.012	0.115	0.065	-0.015	0.065	0.249
	P-value	<0.001	0.868	0.102	0.359	0.836	0.358	<0.001
Basal Respiration	ρ	-0.058	0.014	-0.147	0.153	-0.126	0.014	-0.005
	P-value	0.411	0.840	0.035	0.029	0.073	0.838	0.945
SIR Glucose	ρ	0.011	0.091	-0.004	0.192	-0.226	0.040	0.005
	P-value	0.875	0.194	0.949	0.006	0.001	0.570	0.944
SIR Lignin	ρ	-0.007	0.058	-0.014	0.196	-0.149	-0.001	-0.028
	P-value	0.920	0.410	0.845	0.005	0.033	0.983	0.693

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1320 **Table S12.** Summary results of the one-way ANCOVA analyses carried out with the multifunctionality
1321 as dependent variables. Bacterial richness was a fixed factor and microbial combination was a random
1322 factor nested to bacterial richness. Total bacterial abundance (qPCR; log₁₀-transformed) was included
1323 as a co-variable. df = degrees of freedom. P values below 0.05 are in bold.

Factor	Soil A			Soil B		
	df	F	P-value	df	F	P-value
Abundance of bacteria	1	1.834	0.178	1	0.240	0.182
Richness	3	6.712	0.001	3	4.069	0.012
Microbial combination	63	8.644	<0.001	63	2.462	<0.001

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1349 **Table S13.** Correlations (Spearman) between soil properties (soil total C and pH) with microbial
1350 composition for Field study (n = 43). A = α -Proteobacteria; B = β -Proteobacteria; C = γ -Proteobacteria;
1351 D = Firmicutes; E = Bacteroidetes; F = Actinobacteria.

Soil property	Parameters	A	B	C	D	E	F
Total C	ρ	0.376	0.312	0.592	-0.262	0.250	0.233
	P-value	0.013	0.042	<0.001	0.089	0.106	0.132
pH	ρ	-0.299	0.280	0.006	0.292	0.402	0.242
	P-value	0.051	0.069	0.968	0.058	0.008	0.117

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